

Web-Based Event Management System (EMS)

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A. Design and Implementation of the EMS

There are three types of users in our system; administrator, member (registered user) and guests. If he/she found the new member in registration list, the administrator can view all member information and he/she can also view feedback to update the seminar events if necessary. The administrator can create seminar events, manage seminar events list, view and delete register list, reply and send confirm email, send event tickets to attend the seminars conveniently as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Flow Diagram for Administrator

In Figure 2, the member must log in to register the desire

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, Event management system is used to manage all the activity related to events. This paper is intended to design online web-based event management system. It is used to manage all the seminars and events for a university. Using this system, the members can know the upcoming seminars, past seminars and they can easily register via online. This system is implemented by using J2EE Java Programming Language, Struts and MySQL server 2014 is used to store data.

Keywords: event management system, web-based, java

INTRODUCTION

Social-networking is needed to hold the seminars and to invite target attendees using this website. This will allow like-minded attendees to keep in contact with one another even after an event has passed. This system helps to manage the seminar events and they can also retrieve feedback of last events they have completed. The seminars are arranged for knowledge sharing and the user can be viewed the seminar information, speakers and their profiles before booking the seminar or workshop. Upon successful registration for a seminar, the attendees get a pass in an email with a unique code which has to be printed out and presented when attending the seminars and workshops. The important modules of online event management system are event website, reliable email system and online ticketing.

seminars and to view the applied seminar lists using their email address.

Figure 2 Flow Diagram for Member

After registering the seminar, the member receives the confirm email from administrator to attend or not for it. After that, the member can reply confirm email to administrator and who can accept event ticket to attend the desire seminar. And also, the member can send feedback after attending the seminar.

In Figure 3, the user can browse the information related to the seminars and the user can view seminar events: upcoming seminars and past seminars. If the user wants to attend the seminars, who have to register for it.

Figure 3 Flow Diagram for Guests

B. Test and Results of EMS

In this system, user home page, Events, Contact and About Us menus for guests are as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Home Page

In Events menu, the user can browse the Upcoming Events for recent and future seminars and Past Events for previous seminars can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Event Menu

The user can also contact to admin when he/she wants to know something in contact message box in Contact Menu and who can view detail information in About Us Menu.

Member Log In

If the users interested in the seminars and they want to attend the seminars, they need to create a new member account to become a member, firstly. And then they must log in using this account to register the desired seminars as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Member Log In

Registering Seminar (Member)

When the members want to attend the seminars, they have to register for the desired seminars. Choosing food menu step is necessary for full day seminars while registering but it does not need for half day seminars as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Registering Seminars for full day Menu

After registering the seminar, the member receives the confirm email from administrator to attend or not for it. Administrator chooses the appropriate attendees for the

seminars and send confirmation message including ticket code via email to them. After that, the member can attend the desired seminars using ticket code from administrator. Finally, the member can also send feedback after attending the seminar.

Admin Dashboard

The admin must login with admin username and password to view the admin dashboard. Viewing Dashboard, Adding Event, Viewing Contact Message, Checking Event list, Registration List and Event Feedback Tabs are all the Admin’s functions.

Admin can check Event count, Member count, Feedback count and who can make notes using event calendar in dashboard Menu in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Admin Dashboard

Add Event

In this system, Admin can create new seminars with detailed information including speaker photos and event photos in Add Event Menu as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Creating New Event Menu

Contact Message

Admin can view contact message as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Contact Message Menu

Event List

Admin can view the detailed seminars and who can edit or delete the seminar events. If the seminar date is expired, notification status will appear as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Event List Menu

View Event List

Admin can view the detail seminar event as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 View Detail Seminar Menu

And admin can edit the seminar event as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 Update Seminar Event Menu

Registration List

In registration list menu, Figure 15, admin can view detailed registered users and he/she can choose the appropriate attendees depending on the members’ degree, working experience and so on.

Figure 14 Registration List Menu

Admin can search registered users by date as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Search Registration List by date

Confirmation Letter

After choosing the appropriate attendees, admin press confirm button and email is automatically sent to attendee at the same time. The success message is as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16 Success Message

However, connection errors occur if the connection is available. The error message while sending email is as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17 Error Message

If the sending email is success, the users receive the confirmation letter from admin with detailed information to attend the seminar including ticket code as shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18 Confirmation Letter

Event Feedback

Admin can view the event feedbacks from attendees after finishing the seminars as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19 Event Feedbacks

C. Conclusion

Nowadays, creating an online-event management system becomes popular so this system can support to give valuable seminar event information to the users and make registration via online easily. This system is used to manage all the activity related to event. Moreover, this system reduces time consuming and the members can make registration easily. This will be more suitable to extend this system in order to get online charges for the seminars while making registration process.

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